

Smartrac Project Wins Innovation Product Award at EF ECS 2017

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PING (Printed Intelligent NFC Game Cards and Packaging) integrates NFC technology into playing cards.

Photo: PING

The PING Consortium, consisting of the six companies [Smartrac](#), Cartamundi, Van Genechten Packaging, PragmatIC, imec, and TNO, has been selected as the winner of the Innovation Product Award at the European Forum for Electronics Components and Systems (EF ECS 2017). This award recognises that the PING project paves the way for trillions of interactive objects that will potentially expand the Internet of Things to the mass market.

PING (Printed Intelligent NFC Game Cards and Packaging) is part of the EU Horizon 2020 programme with a goal to enable commercially viable production of smart printed objects.

PragmatIC, imec and TNO focused on the development of ultra-thin, flexible and low-cost Integrated Circuits (ICs); Smartrac contributed its expertise in antenna design; Cartamundi and Van Genechten Packaging

defined the target market applications and established manufacturing processes to integrate the electronics into existing high-volume production lines.

The award has been given to the smart game card and smart packaging concepts produced under PING, which use [RFID](#) embedded within the products to enable them to communicate with a dedicated reader to enhance the user or consumer experience. A video detailing the project is [available on YouTube](#).

Smart packaging can unlock new applications and use cases in logistics and retail. Jeroen Lybaert, Chief Commercial Officer at Van Genechten Packaging, states:

“As Europe’s leading independent packaging innovator we continuously invest in the future of consumer goods. We believe in a connected future for all product packaging. PING unlocks the path to ultra-low cost Smart Packaging.”

For card games and board games, NFC enables new concepts and can help digitalise the gaming experience, bringing traditional experiences into the IoT. Steven Nietvelt, Chief Technology and Innovation Officer of Cartamundi, explains:

“By adding the extra digital dimension, we are able to enable a wide range of exciting new interactive card and board games. In an ever more connected world, consumers expect to blend the real and on-line experiences and this consortium has developed the way to deliver that to our customers”.

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